

Notes

Coordination Compounds of Bivalent Copper with Benzhydrazide of 5-Bromosalicylaldehyde, 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenone and 2, 4-Dihydroxy-valerophenone†

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IN view of the analytical utility^{1,2} and biological activity² of the hydrazones we have isolated some Cu^{2+} complexes with benzhydrazide of 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzophenone and 2, 4-dihydroxyvalerophenone. The present note describes the preparation and characterisation of these compounds.

Experimental

Preparation of ligands: The starting materials, ethylbenzoate, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzophenone and 2, 4-dihydroxyvalerophenone were of high purity. The compounds were synthesised by the general method reported in the literature.

Preparation of complexes: An ethanolic solution of substituted hydrazones were reacted with copper chloride solution in ethanolic acetone in stoichiometric ratio, and the mixture was refluxed for 2 h over a water-bath after raising the pH of the mixture with NaOH solution (1%). On keeping for some time coloured compounds separated out which were filtered, washed with water and dried *in vacua*. The results of the elemental analyses for the complexes are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The analytical results (Table 1) indicate that the complexes have the general formula $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$. The magnetic data show that the complexes are paramagnetic with an effective magnetic moment in the range of 1.88-1.83 B.M., revealing square planar (D_{4h}) geometry around the metal ion.

The electronic spectra of the complexes show a broad peak in the region 16580-18867 cm^{-1} . The peaks observed in the regions 27000-28571 and $\sim 35714 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes may be charge transfer bands. The bands at ~ 25000 and 14900 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the transition $2\text{E} \rightarrow 2\text{T}_2$ of the Cu^{2+} and intra-ligand charge transfer, respectively⁴.

The ir spectral data of ligands and the complexes have been interpreted on the lines of previously reported data. The ligands are capable of undergoing keto \rightleftharpoons enol tautomerism, and hence, they can coordinate in either of these two forms. The spectral studies show that the ligand molecules coordinate to the metal in the enolic form.

The ligands display frequencies in the regions 3400-3300 (enolic OH) and 1350-1300 cm^{-1} (phenolic C—O). The absence of ν_{OH} and negative shift of $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ bands in the complexes suggest the deprotonation of the enolic hydrogen. A strong band at $\sim 1600-1630 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the free ligands is attributable to C=N linkage. In complexes this band is shifted towards lower frequency region suggesting that the imine nitrogen atom is coordinated to the metal ion⁵. Bonding of the nitrogen atom to Cu^{2+} ion have been further substantiated by the appearance of $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ at 500-450 cm^{-1} region. Bands at ~ 3500 (phenolic OH), 1510-1550 (C—O) and 1380 cm^{-1} (C—O and C—C stretch) were observed in the spectra of the free ligands. On complexation the frequency of OH disappears⁶, while that of C—O decreases considerably, indicating the removal of proton during chelation. This has been further supported by the

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compound	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B.M.	$2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow$ 2A_{1g}	2E_g
	Metal	C	H	N			
$[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Br})_2]$	17.28 (16.70)	45.59 (44.15)	2.29 (2.36)	7.61 (7.36)	1.83	18867	28571
$[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)_2]$	16.86 (16.23)	61.98 (64.36)	4.22 (4.08)	7.41 (7.15)	1.85	17470	27690
$[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)_2]$	17.55 (17.01)	59.80 (57.82)	4.68 (4.82)	7.24 (7.49)	1.88	16580	27000

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observation of $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ band in the far-infrared region, in agreement with the earlier observations⁷. Thus, from the above study, it may be concluded that the

ligands act as tridentate and the coordinating sites are phenolic OH, imine nitrogen and enolic OH.

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Characterisation of Some Copper(I) and Silver(I) Complexes Containing Tetraisothoniocyanato-*N*-diaminechromate(III)

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DURING our studies on those coordination compounds in which both cation and anion are complex ions, a series of complexes of various metal(II) ions with amines, oximes, and schiff bases

containing the anions, such as nitrosopentacyanoferrate(II) and hexacyanoferrate(II) ions were prepared and characterised¹⁻⁴. The present note records the synthesis and characterisation of eight copper(I) and silver(I) complexes containing the tetraisothoniocyanato-*N*-diaminechromate(III) ion. These complexes have been assigned to have planar structures on the basis of their magnetic, infrared and electronic spectral data.

Experimental

The complexes were prepared by suspending copper(II) sulphate or silver(I) nitrate in distilled water and adding required amount of ligand in methanol or water. The solution was then refluxed for 4 h and then treated with ammonium tetraisothoniocyanato-*N*-diaminechromate(III) and refluxed again for 2 h. In case of copper(II), sulphurous acid was added to reduce it to copper(I) before refluxing with the ligand. Finally, the complex under study was crystallised out from the solution using petroleum ether and diethyl ether mixture.

Results and Discussion

The molecular formulae proposed for the various complexes are given in Table 1 and are supported by the analytical and molar conductance data. The coordination of various ligands to the two metal ions has been inferred by the infrared data as follows.

- (i) In all the complexes a sharp band appears around 3300 cm⁻¹ which is due to the presence of ammonia, ethylenediamine, urea and thiourea in the complexes. It is assigned to be the N—H stretch, the negative shift of which is due to the coordination of the above ligands to the metal ions.
- (ii) In addition to this, all the complexes also contain two very sharp bands at 2080 and 810 cm⁻¹ which are characteristic of a N-coordinated thiocyanate ion^{5,6}.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA

Sl. no.	Complex	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Molar conductance in PhNO ₂ Ω ⁻¹
			M	thiocyanate	Cr	N	
1.	[Cu(Py) ₂][Cr(NCS) ₄ (NH ₂) ₂]	Reddish yellow	11.23 (11.76)	44.5 (43.01)	10.00 (9.63)	28.42 (28.75)	19.89
2.	[Cu(en)[Cr(NCS) ₄ (NH ₂) ₂]	Yellow	13.92 (14.37)	50.52 (52.56)	10.5 (11.77)	24.93 (25.35)	20.50
3.	[Cu(urea) ₂][Cr(NCS) ₄ (NH ₂) ₂]	Yellow	13.02 (12.64)	46.92 (46.27)	11.00 (10.36)	27.54 (27.90)	24.65
4.	[Cu(thiou) ₂][Cr(NCS) ₄ (NH ₂) ₂]	Orange	12.51 (12.12)	45.00 (44.32)	10.2 (9.92)	26.21 (26.72)	19.50
5.	[Ag(Py) ₂][Cr(NCS) ₄ (NH ₂) ₂]	Pink	18.92 (18.47)	40.2 (39.74)	9.30 (8.90)	19.85 (19.17)	21.05
6.	[Ag(en)][Cr(NCS) ₄ (NH ₂) ₂]	Violet	23.00 (22.2)	48.20 (47.80)	11.10 (10.69)	22.94 (23.04)	Insoluble
7.	[Ag(urea)][Cr(NCS) ₄ (NH ₂) ₂]	Brownish pink	20.10 (19.76)	43.60 (43.52)	10.10 (9.52)	25.12 (25.64)	Insoluble
8.	[Ag(thiou) ₂][Cr(NCS) ₄ (NH ₂) ₂]	Pink	18.97 (19.0)	41.30 (40.16)	9.40 (8.99)	24.95 (24.21)	Insoluble